

Using Reflective Diaries to Study Teachers' Identities in an International Online Teacher Professional Development Programme

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Abstract

This article explores the transformative experience of an international online professional development programme on teachers' identities using evidence from reflective diaries. Membership Categorisation Analysis and Grounded Theory were used to study the reflective diaries of two English Language teachers (the authors). The teachers invoked four identities to make sense of their online experience and recognised that they work in increasingly complex settings where professional development is both goal-oriented and relation-oriented. Their identity construction reflected their awareness of that complexity and the global nature of their profession. The study reveals that a recognition of the multidimensionality of teacher identities is important for understanding the transformative experience of online professional development. Professional development course designers build on such multidimensionality to foster effective educational practices leading to professionalism.

Keywords

Online professional development, teacher professional identity, identity construction, reflective diaries

Introduction

In online Teacher Professional Development (TPD), the integration of information and communication technologies raised a host of new opportunities and challenges. Online TPD cuts across space and time and can be delivered fully online or used together with face-to-face settings to adapt to the varied work situations of teachers (Jiang, Li, & Wang, 2021). Online TPD has been shown to lead not only to improved teaching practices, but also to improved digital competence as a by-product of interaction through the digital medium (Stieben, Pressley, & Matyas, 2021). Stieben et al. (2021) suggest that the provision of professional development programmes through online environments is as effective as in face-to-face situations. It is also subject to the same determinants of success, such as time, duration, material, facilitator role, and learner characteristics (Paesani, 2020). In short, and given the current shift to online education, successful online TPD is successful professional development.

Because of their ubiquity in online TPD, discussion boards have been a favourite site for the study of teacher identities and reflections (Irwin & Hramiak, 2010). Discursive approaches have especially been useful for research on identity construction in discussion forums thanks to the latter's wide adoption in online settings (Delahunty, 2012; Nandi, Hamilton, Harland, &

Warburton, 2011; Patel, 2021). For teachers' reflective practices, the focus on discussion boards is perhaps partly because the study of teacher reflections has lost their allure in favour of a focus on the collaborative-interactive aspect of learning and partly the consequence of a popular understanding of discussion boards as forums for reflection (Levine, 2007). While this view not totally unjustified, we wish to make the case for the continuous relevance of reflective practices outside discussion forums for teacher identity in online TPD. In this paper, we argue that the study of reflective diaries in online TPD settings can still contribute to the fruitful study of teacher identity and positively inform educational practices in the online world. Empirically, the article analyses the reflective diaries of two teachers, the authors as English Language teachers, in order to document the impact of an international online TPD on their identity formation.

Teacher Identities and Reflective Diaries

Teacher identity is a complex issue whose study has evolved following the ebb and flow of identity theories. The conceptualisation of identity as a psychological construct has given way to a view of identity as essentially discursive (Collier, Moffatt, & Perry, 2015; Fina, 2012; Ivanič, 1998; Leaper, 2011). According to Hester and Francis (2000), identities do not operate "above and beyond" discourse (p. 395), but they are themselves reflexively constructed in and through discursive practices (Hughes, 2007; Ivanič, 1998). The reflexive character of discourse is present in settings where discourse is interactional, like in online discussion forums, as well as in reflective diaries that are no less heteroglossic (Hamston, 2006).

Reflective diaries are one crucial tool for teacher development (Glaze, 2002; Jarvis, 1992; McDonough, 1994; Ukrop, Švábenský, & Nehyba, 2019; Vinjamuri, Warde, & Kolb, 2017). Researchers unanimously concur that reflective diaries have a positive impact on learners and teachers alike (Farrell & Macapinlac, 2021; Nurkamto & Sarosa, 2020; Richards & Farrell, 2005). Ukrop et al. (2019) observed that reflective diaries raised teachers' awareness and were useful as a handbook to summarise their learning during training. Studying teachers' reflections on her professional development course, Jarvis (1992) described their diaries as "a useful way of perceiving professional development" (p. 134).

Research on reflective diaries holds perhaps a second-like status in comparison to research on online forums and discussion boards in online settings. However, the two forms of reflection - diaries and discussion forums - are two distinct types of discourse. For one, discussion forums in most online TPD programmes are integral to the course components (Gunawardena, Lowe, & Anderson, 1997; Wang, Chen, & Levy, 2010). Participants in these forums may comply with the task by writing some text without necessarily taking a reflective stance (Farrell & Macapinlac, 2021). As a forum for public reflection, discussion forums are subject to social desirability bias, issues with self-image, and asymmetrical power relations between the facilitator(s) and the participants. In international online TPD, such as the reported on here, considerations of one's self-image may extend to concerns with the image of one's culture and representativeness at the international level.

Reflective diaries, on the other hand, constitute one form of dialogue with the self (Glaze, 2002) where teachers are free to subjectively evaluate their learning in a personal, meaningful way and even voice personal concerns and anxieties that may never find their way to discussion forums. As a form of personal writing, diaries are rarely subject to self-editing and are free from considerations of the social image that might crop into a discussion forum.

The Research Questions

Understandably in the study of identity in online TPD, the preponderant focus on discussion boards and forums is a consequence of a densely connected world where public discourse practices eclipse private forms of discourse (Anderson & Kanuka, 2006), but this does not mean that the study of the latter ceases to contribute to our understanding of identity. To sustain that argument, the present paper examines teacher identity in the reflective space of diary writing and aims to explore online professional development as an ongoing process identity transformation. The paper examines the reflective diaries of two teachers (the authors) written during an online TPD to answer two main research questions:

1. What identities were relevant when the two teachers tried to make sense of the impact of the international online TPD programme?
2. How did these identities account for the intelligibility of the international online TPD programme as a transformative experience?

Methodological Framework

Participants

We are two colleagues who accidentally discovered that we had been participants in two different cohorts of the same international online TPD programme. Discussions about our experiences zoomed in on identity transformations, and we soon became convinced that we shared relatively similar views.

The online TPD programme was delivered by the TESOL association¹ and consisted of three courses. The programme spanned a period from September 21st, 2020 to March 14th, 2021. The titles of the courses are given below:

- Best Practices of Online English Language Teaching
- Online/Mobile Support for English Language Core Competencies Development
- Planning, Organizing, Delivering an Online Course
- Capstone: Putting the Principles into Practice

The programme aimed to help teachers of English around the world develop their teaching competence in online and mobile environments. It should be emphasised reflective diaries were not a formal requirement for the online TPD programme we pursued and that each one of us had kept his reflective diary independently and unknown to the other. Our use of reflective diaries for the programme perhaps emanated from our shared experience in teaching and our belief in the utility of personal reflective diaries for professional development.

Method

We used Membership Categorisation Analysis (MCA) and Grounded Theory to analyse the reflective diaries we wrote in the course of the online TPD programme. The texts in the diaries were approached as a form of reflection-as-action (Jarvis, 1992) that reflexively document our discursive construction of teacher identity (Lepper, 2000). Our aims were to analytically capture the identities we employed in the course of the programme from an insider-outsider-in-between perspective (Milligan, 2016).

Following Whitehead and Lerner (2021) work on self-reference, we employed MCA in order to link our discursive references in the diaries to the context of the online TPD and show how the categories we used for referencing document the transformative impact of that TPD on our identities. Analytically, we heeded the general caveat of MCA practitioners that the analysis of categories must be empirically and demonstrably justified by the discursive data at hand (Schegloff, 1991, 2007). In MCA in general, to be able to link discursive categories to

particular identities is not a methodological nicety but is essentially a methodological imperative.

The coding scheme

One of the authors kept a hand-written diary, whereas the other used an electronic diary. The content of both diaries was transcribed and processed in NVivo 10 using Grounded theory in an iterative process. In the open-coding stage, the focus was initially on all the activities reported from the online TPD programme. In parallel to that, the data were coded for categories and references we used in the diaries, such as teacher, student, colleague, facilitator, peers, in addition to pronominal reference (Irwin & Hramiak, 2010; Ivanič, 1998). The second iteration consisted of axially coding the data to combine the activities into larger sets of what Watson refers to as predicates (Watson, 1978) and to look for general descriptors for the categorical references. We then used selective coding to draw connections between sets of categories and their predicates.

Lastly, selective coding resulted in the identification of four predicates and four categories. For each category a set of predicates is bound and we viewed the link between the category and the predicates as the expression discursive identity, following Antaki and Widdicombe's (1998) principle that, to have an identity "is to be cast into a category with associated characteristics or features" (p. 3). The link between a category and a set of predicates can be either explicit, as when the association is made by the diary writer himself, or else implicit, as when it was understood based on common-sense knowledge of categories and their predicates (Lepper, 2000). The diagram below visually represents the coding process. The solid lines represent an explicit link between a category and a set of predicate and the dotted lines represent implicit links.

Figure 1
The Data Analysis Scheme

Findings

The categories that seemed to us to capture the identity work related to the online TPD are introduced below. Table 1 summarises the main four identities together with their related category-bound predicates.

Table 1

Identities and Their Category-Bound Predicates

Category/Identity	Category-bound predicates
The learner	Reflects on learning and knowledge construction (learning strategies, activities, etc.). Reflects on the usefulness of content.
The practitioner	Links online TPD to students' potential behavioural change. Links online TPD teacher's potential behavioural change.
The community influencer	Discusses past or present situations at the institution/country level. Discusses or recommends future action.
The global connector	Connects with peers in the online TPD. Reflects on global teaching/learning issues in the international context.

The participant as a learner

The category of the learner is an explicit identity reference in reflections in both diaries. Both include entries that show how the new opportunity of learning offered by the programme came just at the right time when we were adapting to the novel context of online teaching imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic. The new demands of remote teaching required that we become familiar with the theoretical and conceptual foundations for teaching English in online learning environments as well as their application in our teaching context. In other words, the identity of learner was relevantly constructed since it mediated our quest for the knowledge that underpins online education— theories of online learning and teaching, characteristics of online learners, the role of the online facilitator, and others aspects of online learning. Some category-bound predicates pertaining to this identity include, not surprisingly, activities related to learning.

A: The readings of this week have been very useful and beneficial. They broadened my perspectives about the different features and functions of the four technology learning environments. They also cleared some of the misconceptions/ ambiguities I had about the implementation of blended learning.

B: The readings for this week helped me to clarify my thoughts on the many ways tech tools are used inside and outside the classroom. I learned a lot from the article on the difference between a technology-rich classroom and a classroom that uses blended learning.

Other entries show a more nuanced and implicit orientation to our identity as learners.

B: I took a quick tour to check all the assignments and readings for this week. I like to do that because it helps me set my goals and know what is expected of me. For this week, I noticed that we were starting to get down to the real work of designing online courses. That's really exciting!!!

In the first part of the opening sentence, the learner refers to required readings and assignments. The requirements show orientation to the online TPD as a formal course with a set of pre-determined tasks and defined expectations necessary for course completion. In other entries, there is evidence that the learner also takes a meta-position (Káplár-Kodácsy & Dorner, 2020) to interact with and evaluate some tasks in the course concerning the fit between the new learning and the current state of knowledge.

A: I also need to devote some time later next week to learn more about the different options and functions of the other technology-enhanced resources.

B: I'm happy that there are readings about active learning and also different videos and articles about it. I feel I'm learning something new, something modern.

As learners, then, our concern was with the acquisition of new knowledge. We reflected on the way that knowledge could be gained primarily for task completion. However, the learner also marginally reflected on the usefulness of the course content for teaching. Indeed, entries in the diaries where the learner looked at the course-by-course content for how it could help in the dilemma of remote teaching constituted one place where our identities as learners began to melt into that of the teacher in the identity continuum (Káplár-Kodácsy & Dorner, 2020).

A: I also realised that blended learning is not a supplementary mode of teaching; it should instead shift instruction in a way that provides an integrated learning experience with a real actual 'blend' of learnings. In one of my readings, I appreciated the kind reminder that 'transferring a face-to-face course to an online format is more than just providing material in digital mode'.

B: This week was all about brainstorming activities for the module plan. All the activities we did this week made me think about the choices I have to integrate into my teaching. I spent a lot of time going back and forth between the course content and the online module I'm designing.

As the excerpts above show, the TPD programme is cast in general descriptions of the benefits gained through the process of learning in the course. The learner didn't begin to consider the specific implications of the online TPD for his teaching practices. Reflections on future behavioural change and the details of classroom practices are activities that constitute the hallmark of the identity of the teacher as a practitioner.

The participant as a practitioner

The practitioners' reflections revealed their concern with two overarching actions that link to potential behavioural change on their part as well as that of their students. On the one hand, the practitioner implicated students in the online TPD by redefining their roles thanks to the programme's perceived impact on the learning situation. Again, the usefulness of the new skills was framed in either a general or specific sense.

A: The LMS [Learning Management System] course would definitely help my students assume responsibility over their own learning while developing their digital literacy skills. Designing activities that revolves around my students' lived experiences and that responds to their needs would to a large extent lead to a successful online learning journey.

B: I will encourage my students to take full advantage of the many many resources provided by technology. They are ready. They are the tech generation.

A: My students will have to create videos, use MindMaps, audios and take full advantage of all the applications they have. In a group activity for example my students can create a video about the way to develop their school. They can write action plans and present them in the videos.

The practitioner ascribed specific roles to the students because the teacher-student pair is what Sacks calls a Standardised Relational Pair (Hester & Eglin, 1997). A Standardised Relational Pair constitutes a locus for rights and obligations that it is enough to invoke one member in the pair to invoke the other. The ascription of new roles for the students in the light of the online TPD experience thus implied new roles for the teacher as well. Indeed, these roles were explicitly mentioned elsewhere in the diaries.

A: The challenge that I may encounter as an online course facilitator has to do with my ability to convince my learners to persist as they interact with their coursemates in my online courses.

B: Plagiarism is a big big problem. I have to be more explicit and my students need to have all the information they need to avoid it.

A: I'm afraid that working on tasks may require a good level of English proficiency among my students who may struggle to use English correctly while solving a task through my Canvas LMS. I need to tailor activities according to my students' diverse needs and wants.

It can be seen that the invocation of the identity of the teacher as a practitioner makes the category of student relevantly present under the Standardised Relational Pair quality. Writing about a potential behavioural change in the excerpts below, A explicitly mentions the students in his reflection as one party who would be affected by the transformation.

A: I also feel that their reluctance to try online education relates to their lack of basic technical skills and adequate training on how to use their LMS. I'm confident that a small number of students will certainly show interest and enthusiasm to be active learners in their online course, but the majority may resist change.

In addition to the assignment of new roles, the practitioners conceptually reframed past and future practices against a transitional and continuously updated state of knowledge. Whereas reflections on past experiences changed the way they were perceived only, reflections on the future practices referred to intentional behavioural change and to desirable outcomes that would, or should, be achieved.

A: For a successful online learning journey, activities should be cognitively stimulating and socially engaging. They should also be designed in such a way that they contribute to the creation of a community of learners who work together as a team to solve real-life problems.

B: I fell in love with this idea of active learning and now I have all the details I need to put it into practice in my classes. I will get students to role play with me just-in-time teaching. I don't want my students to expect me to do it ALL the time.

It may be noticed that the practitioner limited the setting of the transformative change to the classroom only. The community influencer, in contrast, claimed a territory that sometimes went beyond the classroom and even the school setting itself.

The participant as a community influencer

Like the practitioner, the community influencer moved back and forth between past, present, and future activities in his reflections. Two related characteristics defined the latter. First, the locational formulation of the setting (Schegloff, 1972) went beyond the classroom. The set of activities reported took place at the institutional setting of the school, the local arena of the

community, or at the national level of the country. Second, this categorisation shifted from seeing oneself as a member in a Standardised Relational Pair of teacher-student to membership in a group of colleagues. The community influencer, either explicitly or implicitly, implicated group membership whenever he used such categories as colleagues, teachers in my community, teachers in my country, or other teachers; while implying that he, the community influencer, is part of the group.

To the extent that the influencer invoked the community, he did one of three things. First, he built an all-inclusive membership in the collection, where the collection as a whole acted in unison.

A: As teachers, we need to kindle our students' interest in taking online courses. I think that our task is to help our students see the relevance as to why they need to interact with their mates online. They should also recognise the importance of developing their positive attitudes about their capabilities and their engagement in online learning.

B: In my school, the other teachers and I have been trying to jump into the world of online teaching for years now. We were overwhelmed and now this pandemic increased our sense of despair.

Second, the community influencer, having invoked the community as a collection, explicitly set his activities in contrast to those of other members within it. This form of 'identification reformulation' (Silverman, 1998) re-defined the activities of the community influencer as better informed by knowledge not accessible to the other members of the community. Still a member of the group, the community influencer was now better informed; so he could re-define, so to speak, the boundaries of the group as a whole.

A: As we engage in our online courses with our students, it is useful to think about ways to engage people/teachers with the black hat perspective in the conversation. We need to build a community of learning!

B: Many of my colleagues begin their classes by reviewing all the grammar lessons from the previous year. I used to do that too, but it always felt wrong. For other years, I used to start with writing because I felt that grammar should serve a purpose. How uninformed we all were!!! Now I know where to start.

Third, the community influencer set his reflections in a temporal timeline from the past to the present to the future. Whereas the practitioner framed his future actions as plans to carry out, the community influencer framed many of them as collective actions/ recommendations for the community. In other words, any plans made by the community influencers were contingent on the level of influence they both had within the boundaries of the setting they perceived as feasible.

A: The impression I usually get after friendly discussions with my colleagues about the development of the listening skill among our students is that this is the least used skill in our classrooms. The fact that our English curriculum doesn't include the listening skill in the end of term examinations makes teachers and students skip over this skill. Ample focus is usually devoted to helping learners develop other linguistic components namely: Reading, writing, grammar, vocabulary, functions, speaking etc. Although the listening skill is present in each unit of the textbook, teachers struggle to finish the course by paying more attention to the former components.

A: There is always room for reflection and modification because things might work better if we choose to consider the different perspectives that our students and colleagues suggest.

B: Establishing guidelines and standard procedures in the institution is a good thing to do. We didn't take them seriously before. I now can say which ones can work for us.

At this level, we can notice that the context of possible action has expanded from the classroom to that of the school and/or the country. The expansion of the connections went even further thanks to the international nature of the TPD program.

The participant as a global connector

The online TPD programme targeted teachers from different countries around the world. Its heterogeneity brought different cultures, settings, and teaching philosophies to the front as a matter for reflection, not only in the online discussion forums but also in our diaries. Compounded with the mixed-up composition of the class was the similarity at the international level of the teaching contexts due the Covid-19 pandemic (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020).

The effects of these factors were quite apparent in some entries in the diaries. One of the clearest examples of the invocation of the global connector was the use of the category classmates to refer to the other teachers in the online TPD. Interestingly, the use of this identity increased at the last week of each course and towards the end of the programme.

A: My classmates share a lot of interesting stuff. I personally benefited a lot from their reflections and suggestions.

B: Talking to my peers in the discussion forums is so helpful. I can read about their experiences and I can get feedback on mine. Just like me, they are trying a lot of new things to make their classes engaging.

The category-bound predicates of the identity of the global connector referred to the synergy that came from being a member of a class with all the benefits that could bring its members—sharing, collaborating, discussing, and other group-related activities.

A: I believe I still need to receive feedback from my collaborator partners to check how they will react to the tasks and the questions. This will certainly help me find answers to the questions I raised last week.

In addition to connections with coursemates, the other key theme in the reflections of the global connector was his reference to global issues that affected the international context of teaching. The problems shared by the international participants in the programs and the potential of technology to surmount them constituted a big part of the reflections of the global connector.

A: It seems to me that the international status of English should be considered when designing listening activities. Students should be presented with language content that covers the use of a variety of 'Englishes'.

B: Teachers of the word! Unite! I think that should be the motto of this crisis we are going through now. The experience of my peers in the programme is not that different from mine: frustration, lack of equipment, loss, and impotence.

Discussion

The analysis identified four identities that we constructed to make sense of the impact of the online TPD programme using the apparatus of Grounded Theory and MCA. The identities of the teacher as a learner, practitioner, community influencer, and global connector mediated the TPD programme. These four identities also related the programme's content to its outcomes and to any potential engagement (Ji, 2021). The identities thus offered an answer to the first research question concerning what identities we, as participants in an online TPD programme, constructed. It is important to stress that the four identities described, though discursively related to the context of their use, may cut across other identities in different contexts (Farrell & Macapinlac, 2021). However, we do not consider identity transformation as a linear transition from one sub-identity to another, but more in line with the constructivists' understanding of identity as a construct whose relevance participants establish by the contextual demands of the situation (Antaki & Widdicombe, 1998; Lepper, 2000).

To address the second question of how the online TPD programme constituted a transformative experience, it is possible to highlight several aspects of the four identities constructed. First, it might be observed that the identity of learner and practitioner are goal-oriented, instrumental identities, whereas the last two, the community influencer and the global connector, are relational. The goal-oriented identities document a process of change as it relates to the impact of professional development at the cognitive and behavioural levels (Ji, 2021). It is this aspect of online TPD transformation that is often captured in empirical studies (Ji, 2021; Kayapinar, 2018), or in studies of online discussion forums where reflection is purposefully done on course material for the sake of bringing that change to the surface. The relational feature, on the other hand, is often observed but rarely studied in-depth, even though connectivism characterises not only students' learning, but also teachers' practices and professional development. In our experience, some of the connections we made with other participants from around the world morphed into a more lasting commitment to continue sharing experiences through other media and a mutual engagement to develop our students and ourselves. Thus, it is possible that, for online TPD programmes in general, their transformative impact at both the behavioural and relational level extend well after the programme's formal completion. Figure 2 summarises the identities and the types of relations constructed through the course.

Figure 2

Identity and Identity Expansion After the Online TPD

The rectangular framework in the diagram represents the context of the online TPD programme with the four identities constructed therein. These identities and the types of transformations they represent overflow into two main directions. First, teachers use their experiences to impact their relations with their students and other teachers in the formal institutional context, where teaching and learning takes place. In addition, as teachers continue to grow professionally, they may bring their identities to bear on other future professional development settings. The double-headed large arrows represent the flow of identities in these two distinct but intimately related settings. The smaller arrows represent the potential overflow into larger contexts in the future. The multiplicity of identities constructed thus enables teachers to expand their membership into multiple communities at once. The effectiveness of online TPD can in turn be measured by its impact on the number and density of their community connections.

The four identities also make sense in terms of the reflection-action cycle for professional development popularised by Schön (Moon, 1999) and imported to the teaching profession by many scholars (Farrell, 2011; Farrell & Macapinlac, 2021; Gabryś-Barker, 2014; Jarvis, 1992; Richards & Farrell, 2005). They usher to a world where teacher professional development will likely expand in a more mediated and globalised world. In such a context, online TPD offers opportunities for updating one's knowledge, but they also affect teacher identity construction in such ways that well-entrenched and nascent identities co-exist and interact. More importantly, the analysis points to the way reflections take place in a necessarily multidimensional space where teachers project the local particularities of their profession into a global context. Thrown into the middle of the Covid-19 pandemic and aware of the opportunities online professional development can bring, teachers approach online TPD as a form of professional expansion that is also crucial to the constructive character of their identity. In addition, the findings of the present work concur with those of other researchers who identified more or less the same identities for teachers (Farrell, 2011). For the experienced language teacher, Farrell (2011) posits a continuum of identity roles that run from one pole of ready-made identity roles to individually-created ones in the opposite pole (p. 60). Central to the gamut of identities posited by Farrell is the role of the teacher as a learner and collaborator. The latter in Farrell's taxonomy is similar to the identity of the community influencer identified earlier in this article; but the influencer straddles more than just a community limited by the physical walls of the institution. Thanks to the availability of online TPD opportunities, teachers are likely to expand their network as collaborators using the many tools provided by the web and potentially turn into influencers.

The present work has some practical implications for professional development in general and online teacher training, education, and development in particular. The starting point of the present research paper was the observation that diaries, as one discursive form teachers' reflections are structured (Gabryś-Barker, 2009, 2014; Nurkamto & Sarosa, 2020), were relegated to the shadows due to the heavy focus on public forms of reflection in discussion forums. We suggest that diaries be employed to complement discussion board reflections and not be replaced by them. Diaries may embody teachers' reflections that are not necessarily limited by the logistics of online professional development. They may contain critical reflections on the self, critique of the programme, and a host of remarks inaccessible through other means. Reflective diaries proved their utility for the professional development of teachers and therefore merit more than lip service in online TPD. The personal element in reflective diaries guards against seeing reflection as yet another task to complete for the sake of checking all the formal requirements of an online TPD programme.

Conclusion

Research on professional development has a long tradition of probing the use and usefulness of reflective diaries and identity construction (Farrell & Macapinlac, 2021). In online TPD, the study of public media through which identity is constructed takes precedence. The present article has endeavoured to show that a focus on diaries can complement findings on teacher identity and reflective practices in online TPD. Although the findings lack generalizability, they concur with those from previous research (Farrell, 2011). The expansion of teachers' domains is likely to result in a bigger taxonomy of identities and different roles. As a result, future research can use a comparative perspective to study teacher identity in the open, dialogic spaces of discussion forums and the equally dialogic, but more private, tools such as personal diaries. In short, teachers construct different identities in complex ways that reflect the complexity of their job inside and outside the classroom. Glimpsing at those ways may point to the transformative experiences of being a teacher.

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